

New Insights in Structural Design of Composite Rotor Blades for Helicopters

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ABSTRACT

About 50 all-composite helicopter main rotor blades have been designed to date. More than 15 of these have reached either limited or full production status. Eight others are approaching production. This paper reviews the different design concepts and materials that have been applied to many of these blades. Various design solutions to the problems of root end and drag link attachments, spar and blade transition sections, and tip weight and tip cap attachments are described. Blade fabrication methods are reviewed. Methods of analyzing the problem areas are described. Finally, the service experience with US military blades made from composites is summarized with comments on present and future trends in the technology.

INTRODUCTION

At least 50 different all-composite main rotor blades have been designed to date. About 25 of these have been flight tested and over 15 have progressed to limited or full production status. Table 1 contains a list of these blades. This review will be mainly concerned with the composite blade designs that have advanced to and beyond flight test status. The emphasis will be on US Army blade designs because of the authors affiliations, interests, and experiences, and the fact that much of the composite blade development work has been US Army sponsored.

There have been about 25 different US Army composite rotor blade programs underway since 1970. Six of the blades have reached flight status. They are:

- 1) the CH-47 Advanced Geometry Blade (1972)
- 2) the AH-1 Multi Tubular Spar Blade (1975)
- 3) the CH-47D Composite Blade (1978)
- 4) the AH-1S Improved Main Rotor Blade (1980)
- 5) the AH-64 Prototype Blade (1981)
- 6) the BO-105 Bearingless Main Rotor (1981)

There were other recent and interesting Army composite blade programs. Perhaps the most interesting and ambitious one, by virtue of blade size and load levels, was the HLH blade which has been in storage for the last several

years. However, of the aforementioned list the most significant ones (in the sense of their progression to operational status or promise of such) are the CH-47D, AH-1S, and AH-64 blades. This paper will emphasize the features of these three designs. The design concepts, materials, fabrication methods, and structural analyses, will be compared. The results of their flight service experience will be reviewed. Finally, the overall experience will be summarized, some problems addressed, and indications of future directions suggested.

HISTORY

In 1947 Cornell Aero Lab. built what were probably the first rotor blades which used some fiberglass reinforced plastic (FRP) construction. These blades had wood spars with FRP skins. They flew on a Sikorsky R-5. In 1953 Glenview Metal Products built a GMP-2 Flyride helicopter with a main rotor blade of laminated spruce forward of the 30% chord and FRP skins on a balsa wood core aft of the 30% chord. In 1956 Prewitt Aircraft Company built three sets of research rotors for the Piasecki HUP-2 aircraft. One set was made of stainless steel, one of titanium, and one of FRP. The composite blade had a wood spar. The Gyrodine XRON-1 introduced in 1956 had all-fiberglass blades on some later versions. Parsons also built two different experimental blades for the H-21 from stainless steel and FRP in the same period. One of the composite blades failed in the whirl test stand and was never flight tested.

The early 1960's saw the introduction of several composite rotor blade designs. Among these were the Kaman H43-B blade of 1960 which had a wood core with FRP skins on the afterbodies. The Bolkow BO-103 helicopter which first flew in 1961 had a single main rotor blade made of FRP. The Boeing Vertol CH-47 blade of 1961 consisted of a steel D spar with aluminum ribs and FRP skins. In 1962 Kaman flew an all-FRP blade on the HH-43B helicopter.

1968 was the year that marked the beginning of the all-boron Advanced Geometry Blade program for the Boeing Vertol CH-47. An all-FRP version of this blade was designed and built in the same time period. Both these blades were flight tested in the early 1970s. By this time the future of helicopter rotor blades was clearly pointed in the direction of all-composite construction.

DESIGN CONCEPTS

This section considers the material/structural design concepts that have been applied to most of the recent Army composite blades plus some designs from other sources. Figure 1 contains a collection of mid span blade cross sections (drawn to different scales) that illustrate the materials and their distributions and orientations. The D spar has been the most popular concept with C spars a close second. Multi tubular spars have been used in several military designs for improved ballistic tolerance. Full depth sandwich afterbodies are the most popular aft blade concept in the US. Foam core sandwich is more prevalent in European designs.

Figure 2 shows some of the different root end and drag link attachment concepts that have been used in recent composite blade designs. The "wrap around lug" concept is the dominant one today. The early "coke bottle" concept of the AGB is uncertain and difficult to reproduce. The only competing root attachment concept is the "drilled and bolted" one of which the H-3 and Sea King designs are typical. There is considerable interest in attaching blades directly to the hub or hub yoke bearings by incorporating the blade flapping element into the blade design. Except for the few bearingless rotor designs this concept has not been put to use. It poses some practical difficulties when R&M and blade folding requirements are considered.

Figure 3 shows some of the spar wrap transition concepts whereby the mid span spar material transitions into the root end attachment region. This has been accomplished by rotating a flat segment of the spar pack 90°, wrapping it around a root end lug, and then rotating back through 90° into the spar cap

plane once more. This can also be accomplished either by wrapping around a horizontal root end lug or by simply not twisting the spar pack as it wraps around a vertical lug.

Figure 4 shows some of the concepts for transitioning the centrifugal force and the twist and drag moments out of the aft blade and trailing edge longos into the root end. This has been done by increasing the afterbody skin thicknesses at the root end, providing a diagonal close out rib, or in some cases carrying the trailing edge longos directly into the drag link attachment lug.

Figure 5 shows some tip weight attachment concepts. These have been held in place by wrapping the spar cap material around them in a continuous manner, entrapping them within tapering spars, wrapping cap material around plugs or knobs on the ends of the tip weights, or bonding or bolting them to the main spar and outer skin material.

The concepts for attaching the tip cap rib or tip cap fairing to the blade all seem to fall into the category of either bonding or mechanically attaching them to the blade extremity. These are typified by the designs in Figure 6.

FABRICATION METHODS

Probably the most important engineering accomplishment opening the way to practical composite rotor blades was the development of automated fabrication methods. Automation offered a solution to the two main drawbacks found in early composite blades: namely, high hand labor costs and inconsistent physical and mechanical properties due to excessive operator handling of the composite constituents.

The progenitor of the CH-47D blade was the Advanced Geometry Blade (AGB). The blade (both the glass and boron versions) was to a large degree hand made. A hand laid up "C" spar and skin, using prepreg tapes, were first cured leaving the trailing edge open. This assembly was then placed on its nose, the trailing edge opened and the core material "stuffed" in. The blade was finally vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave. The design, fabrication and testing program on the AGB blades was highly successful. However, cost projections and doubts about physical consistency discouraged their immediate production.

Bolkow, through its own research, undertook the design and production of the BO-105 composite blade. The blade was largely hand laid up but, through precise process control and exceptional workmanship, was able to overcome manufacturing variabilities and arrive at a highly reliable, exceptionally maintainable blade. The blade has proven to have life cycle cost benefits highly advantageous to users. The blade skin is first laid up by hand in two open female molds. Roving tapes of approximately twice the blade length are impregnated with resin and placed in the mold. They are then wound around the attachment bushing and back toward the blade tip. The foam core and the balance weight are then inserted into the lower mold. The upper and lower molds are then pressed together and oven cured.

Encouraged by Bolkow's success the US industries continued to pursue composite blade technology. The next blade concept leading toward the CH-47D was the HLH blade. Many fabrication innovations were developed for this blade in order to reduce labor costs. The "coke bottle" blade root retention concept of the AGB was dropped in favor of the "wrap around lug" concept (see Figure 2) to accommodate much easier fabrication techniques.

The next blade in this family was the all-composite blade for UH-61, the losing competitor in the UTTAS competition. Specialized automated fabrication techniques were developed around the automated tape layup concept. The production fabrication technique developed for this blade included the capability to automatically layup all composite elements. The facilities developed

for the UTTAS were planned for application to the CH-47D at this time. The basic tape layup system utilized was the Goldsworthy Automated Tape Layup System (ATLAS) (Fig. 7). This is a six axis machine that can lay tape to virtually any configuration. However, the trend shifted toward the development of techniques requiring simple machines rather than sophisticated six axis machines. There were two schools of thought on the matter at that time: one was in favor of laying a completed detail ready for sub assembly; the second favored the layup of simple, flat patterns in multiples. The first approach is more sophisticated but eliminates hand assembly. The second requires less sophisticated machinery but more hand work. In either case automation was absolutely essential. The issue was unresolved at that time since neither the Boeing UTTAS nor HLH went into production.

The CH-47D blade is a refinement of the manufacturing techniques and specialized automated layup system developed on the HLH and UTTAS. Cost projections indicate that by minimizing hand labor and careful process control this blade will achieve initial cost values lower than its metal counterparts. The ATLAS six axis machine is used extensively in the fabrication of layups for the CH-47D so it would appear that the trend is toward minimizing hand layups at the expense of sophistication.

The AH-1S production blade evolved in a slightly different manner. The manufacturing methods applied to this blade were conceptually proven in the earlier AH-1 Multi-Tubular Spar (MTS) blade development. A wet filament winding technique used extensively for pressure bottles and light weight liquids storage tanks was explored and applied to the MTS blade (Fig. 8). Blade spars, root reinforcements and skins were automatic wet filament wound, assembled and co-cured into a rotor blade of exceptional consistency with low manufacturing cost potential. A current drawback is that most winding processes require resins of lower molecular weight than other layup procedures and they are harder to control with regard to resin content.

Blade design, tooling design, and manufacturing processes are intimately related in wet filament winding and must be developed jointly. Unlike metal design where the raw materials are fully characterized with standard mechanical properties, the raw materials in a composite structure have few inherent properties until they are assembled and cured into a finished part.

A very important part of the wet filament winding process is the resin impregnator. This device guides dry rovings from as many as 18 spools through heated rollers that impregnate a metered amount of resin into the rovings. The impregnator is an integral part of the tube winding machine which winds spar tubes, spar caps, skin, and reinforcing laminates. The skin and reinforcing laminates are slit longitudinally and laid out flat as broad-goods. Longitudinal members (longos) are wound on a long turntable, again utilizing the impregnator.

The MTS blade was molded in a two part, closed cavity mold. Half of the components, including root end bushings and tip weights, were placed on each mold half and held in place by a bondable vacuum diaphragm that remained in the blade. The five spar tubes were positioned by jigs on the lower half of the mold. Then the upper half of the mold was inverted and clamped to the lower half. These components were co-cured to achieve a secure chemical bond. The blade was formed from the outside in, with the mold forming an accurate and repeatable outer contour. The spar tubes served as tooling in the curing process. After the mold was closed, these tubes were pressurized to force all the other components into intimate contact for curing.

The final AH-1S blade design and fabrication technique was extrapolated from the MTS concept. The blade was procured using a "design to cost" contracting concept to insure that purchase costs of the composite blade would be competitive with conventionally fabricated metal blades. Hard production tooling was used in the fabrication of this blade. Closed metal molds were

used for curing the filament wound spar and trailing edge spline, and for the final assembly bond. A neoprene jacket on the brass tip weight was vulcanized in place in a closed mold. The spar was filament wound on hard extractable spar mandrels which provide good weight control and internal geometry. The solid leading edge filler that is wound into the spar was produced by a semiautomated process closely related to conventional filament winding. Final assembly bonding was accomplished by assembling the spar, spline, uncured skins and core in the bottom half of the bond fixture, installing the fixture top, and curing.

The AH-64 composite blade fabrication technique is also a direct descendant of the MTS blade concept. Fabrication refinements were incorporated into the basic wet filament winding process developed for the MTS design. This included winding the tubular spars in "D" shapes rather than circular (in order to achieve less distortion and fiber shift during curing) and winding longos in a racetrack machine (where the fiber dispenser moved along the racetrack for better fiber distribution and tension control).

The feasibility and viability of composite rotor blades is firmly grounded on the two fundamental automated fabrication techniques of automated prepreg tape layup and wet filament winding. Development of these techniques and variants revolutionized rotor blade design and ushered in fibrous composites to their status as the standard rotor blade material of the present and foreseeable future.

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

This section contains examples of adequate structural analysis of three problem areas in blade design; the root end fitting, the transition from root end to mid span, and the tip weight attachment. The root end analysis relates to the YAH-64 prototype wrap around lug design. The transition analysis relates to the composite CH-46 and CH-47 blades. The tip weight analysis refers to the AH-1S composite blade design.

The root end of the YAH-64 prototype blade shown in Figure 2 experienced some premature failures during full scale fatigue testing. Originally the stress concentrations in the longos that wrap around the root end pin (and bushing) had been estimated by using an empirical handbook formula for stresses adjacent to loaded holes. Subsequently, two different finite element analyses were run on the same design. The first, based on the sketch in Figure 9, was a two dimensional analysis using rectangular and triangular elements with membrane, shear, and bending stiffness in the SPAR code. Using this analysis the peak stress concentrations in the fiber direction was substantially higher than the empirical factor. A second finite element analysis was done based on the three dimensional model of Figure 9. These elements were all pentahedrons and hexahedrons in the EISI/EAL code (which is similar to SPAR). The three dimensional analysis accounts for pin bending and shear deformations and the resultant secondary distortions of the lug material. The components of stress in the fiber direction did not change significantly but the other stress components did. The magnitudes of the stresses with components normal to the fibers, though low by comparison to the fiber stresses, were high with respect to the transverse strength of the unidirectional material. These off-axis stresses were probable contributors to the premature fatigue failures of the test blades. The empirical lug stress factors used in design were not only unconservative, by a factor of almost two, but were not capable of making any estimate of those stresses having components normal to the fibers. The typical elementary assumption of sinusoidally varying pressure between a lug and a pin was not close to the finite element results for the complex pin pressure distribution. A composite design, unlike metals, requires careful attention be given to all the components of multiaxial stress in almost every realistic application.

The next example is of an adequate analytical treatment of a rotor design

problem involving the transition section of a composite CH-46/CH-47 type blade as shown in Figure 3. The inboard end of this rotor blade design transitions from a mid span airfoil contour into the compact blade retention region. The load in the trailing edge and aft fairing must be transferred into the main spar over a short spanwise distance. Strength of material methods are generally inadequate for this analysis. Shear lag analysis and two dimensional elastic analysis is an improvement but the resulting detailed stress information is still either crude or totally absent. As a result three dimensional NASTRAN analysis has been applied to this problem. Figure 10 shows the finite element idealization of the structure. The elements used are triangular and quadrilateral membranes for the skin and trailing edge materials and hexahedron and wedge elements for the thick spar covers and the honeycomb sandwich. The separate effects of centrifugal forces, blade bending moments, and twisting moments on the transition section stresses were resolved in separate runs. For level flight the critical element was at the inboard cover skin at the beginning of the transition section as shown in Figure 10. The margins of safety from the analysis were adequate and verified by subsequent bench and flight tests. This design has performed well in several years of service with the US Navy and Army.

The final example of composite blade analysis involved the AH-1S improved main rotor blade. This composite replacement for an older metal blade ended up weighing considerably less than the metal design, necessitating the addition of a large tip weight to restore the blade rotary inertia. The tip weight attachment concept is shown in Figure 5. The D shaped tip weight is encased in rubber and molded into the main spar. A two dimensional shear lag analysis of the tip weight bond stress due to centrifugal forces (see Figure 11) showed the peak shear stresses in the rubber to be relatively low. Also the outer spar was tapered in order to trap the tip weight in the spar in case the rubber layer failed. Despite these precautions a single tip weight was thrown after several hundred hours of operation. Fractographic analysis of the failed parts showed progressive fatigue failure in shear of the rubber around the inboard end of the weight which was probably aggravated by inhomogeneity of the filled rubber material. The presence of a sharp leading edge on the tip weight permitted the weight to cut through the spar leading edge. This action was further abetted by a nonuniform layer of rubber which was thinnest at the leading edge. A finite element analysis of the normal stress distribution around the periphery of the D shaped cross section (see Figure 12) showed a highly nonuniform normal stress distribution instead of what was assumed to be uniform. The inadvertent rubber thickness variation also led to a high shear strain concentration at the same location. Microscopic examination showed pulverized rubber particles imbedded deeply between layers of leading edge spar material that had been progressively cut by the sharp edged tip weight before total separation of the weight. This three dimensional stress problem was relieved by mechanically attaching the tip weight to the spar caps, rounding off the sharp leading edge of the tip weight, and taking precautions in the vulcanizing of the rubber weight cover to assure uniform layer thickness.

This example points out another general lesson to be learned in the analysis of composite or metal structures. There is a mistaken tendency to analyze structures as they are drawn rather than as they are actually being built. Worst cases of manufacturing tolerances and mismatches should be accounted for in the analysis.

SERVICE EXPERIENCE

The three US military composite main rotor blades which have seen significant service experience are the Navy/Marine CH-46 blade and the Army CH-47D and AH-1S blades. The CH-46 blade has the most flight and calendar time with both shipboard and land based service. The mean composite blade flight hours between maintenance actions, failures, depot repairs, and scrapings all represent at least an order of magnitude improvement over the metal blades. The total composite CH-46 blade hours, as of April 1982, was 300,000. Over

1100 blades have been delivered. The high time blade has about 2000 hours of flight service. The fiberglass CH-46 blades have met and surpassed every specified objective with respect to their operational effectiveness and general suitability. Depot level repairs and blade scrappage has been virtually eliminated. Maintenance costs for the composite blade are running about one fourth of the metal blade maintenance costs. The program is considered an unqualified success by the Navy and Marines. Similarly encouraging results have been obtained on the Army CH-47D composite blade program where a total of 425 blades are now in service, beginning in 1981. The highest time composite blade has over 1250 flight hours. The Army fleet has accumulated over 10,000 flight hours. The commercial CH-47 fleet has over 30,000 flight hours on the same blade design. The record of maintenance actions is very similar to the CH-46 data.

With the exception of the tip weight retention problem discussed earlier the service experience with the AH-1S composite has been excellent. Over half the blades have been fabricated on a production run of almost 1000. The high time blades have exceeded 1000 flight hours. The total blade flight time is over 100,000 hr. The new tip weight retention bolts are being retrofitted onto all of the blades in service and are being applied to all of the newly fabricated blades.

The outlook for improvements in rotor blade operating costs with composite blades is most encouraging. Similar results have been reported by Westlands, Aerospatiale, and MBB on their composite blades. The BO-105 blades that have been in production for 10 years total over 1,000,000 blade flight hours with the high time blades in the 10,000 hour range. A debonding problem between the composite and metal root end fitting has been the only significant maintenance problem reported.

CONCLUSIONS

Composite helicopter rotor blades are rapidly becoming the industry standard. It is likely that metal blades will eventually be replaced by composite blades in all current and future Army helicopters. However, the path to successful accomplishment of this goal could be troublesome if attention to detail or the understanding of composites characteristics are slighted. The advantage of composites is that they permit a designer to focus strength and stiffness along the load paths to achieve high efficiency. However, if unexpected load path changes cause high matrix or interlaminar stresses the composite has little inherent tolerance compared to isotropic metals. Therefore, more detailed analysis methods are needed particularly in critical areas.

As more and more all-composite rotor blades of various materials and fabrication techniques are placed in the hands of users, more perceptions of their strengths and weaknesses are starting to emerge. These perceptions still need to be proven right or wrong by continuing investigation.

- a) The concerns about moisture absorption and solar UV radiation have diminished to a readily solvable detail design problem causing no more difficulty with composites than conventional metal construction.
- b) Analytical and test methods that disregard multiaxial and secondary stresses and strains (which designers and analysts have learned to safely apply to blades made of isotropic materials) may not apply to anisotropic materials. All the inherent assumptions must be reevaluated.
- c) Damage tolerant and fail safe concepts should not be overlooked in composite blade design because of the popular conceptions that composites have a "soft" failure mode. The disciplined approach of anticipating failures, establishing failure rates by test or analysis, devising timely detection methods is still necessary to

insure "on-condition" design of composite components.

- d) Manufacturing tolerances and allowances may be greater and at the same time more critical in composite design. They should be carefully considered in the stress analysis.
- e) Material and process specifications must be stringently defined and strictly adhered to.

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TABLE 1: COMPOSITE MAIN ROTOR BLADE/DESIGNS

1956	Parsons H-21	1978	Aerospatiale SA-365N *
1961	MBB Heli Trainer	1978	Sikorsky H-3
1962	MBB B-103 *	1978	Kaman OH-58
1962	Kaman HH-43B	1979	Hughes AH-64 **
1964	Gyrodine XRON-1*	1979	Kaman AH-1 (K747) *
1966	Bell UH-1	1979	Boeing Vertol CH-47D *
1968	Boeing Vertol CH-47 (B/EP)	1979	Aerospatiale AS-355 *
1968	Boeing Vertol CH-47 (FRP)	1980	Lockheed X-Wing
1971	MBB BO-105 *	1980	Bell 212 *
1972	Sikorsky CH-53	1981	Aerospatiale SA-332 *
1973	Aerospatiale SA-360 *	1981	Hughes 500D
1973	Fiber Science OH-6 (LoRCS)	1981	Hughes (NASA)
1974	Lockheed Geodesic Truss	1982	Bell 406 (AHIP) **
1975	Bell 206L	1982	Kaman H-2 **
1975	Sikorsky XH-59A (ABC)	1982	Westlands Sea King **
1975	Aerospatiale SA-341 *	1982	Sikorsky UH-60 **
1975	Fiber Science AH-1G (MTS)	1982	Aerospatiale AS-366 *
1976	Boeing Vertol HLH	1982	Aerospatiale HH-65A *
1976	Boeing Vertol UH-61A	1982	Agusta A129 **
1976	Aerospatiale SA-330 *	1983	Boeing Vertol XV-15
1977	Bell 214 *	1983	Westlands/Agusta EH-101 **
1977	Aerospatiale AS-350 *	1983	Boeing Vertol R&D **
1977	Boeing Vertol CH-46 *	1983	MBB/Kawasaki BK-117 **
1978	Boeing Vertol OH-58	1983	Westlands S-61 **
1978	Bell OH-58	1983	Westlands SH-3 **

(* In production)

(** Production anticipated)

FIGURE 1. BLADE CROSS SECTIONS

FIGURE 2. ROOT END AND DRAG LINK ATTACHMENTS

FIGURE 3. SPAR TRANSITION CONCEPTS

FIGURE 5. TIP WEIGHT ATTACHMENTS

FIGURE 4. BLADE TRANSITION CONCEPTS

FIGURE 6. TIP CAP ATTACHMENTS

FIGURE 7. AUTOMATED TAPE LAYUP SYSTEM (ATLAS)

FIGURE 8. WET FILAMENT WINDING NON-CIRCULAR SHAPE

FIGURE 9. FINITE ELEMENT MODELS OF AH64 ROOT LUG.

FIGURE 10. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF BLADE TRANSITION SECTION.

FIGURE 11. SPANWISE DISTRIBUTION OF SHEAR STRESSES BETWEEN TIP WEIGHT AND BLADE SPAR

FIGURE 12. NORMAL (PRESSURE) STRESS DISTRIBUTION AROUND A TAPERED TIP WEIGHT DUE TO CENTRIFUGAL FORCE.